

Smart Energy Meter Using Telegram BOT

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Abstract

Increasing demand for electrical energy and efficient utilization of energy have led to the development of intelligent metering systems. This paper, therefore, presents the design and implementation of a smart energy meter based on an ESP32 microcontroller integrated with current and voltage sensors for real-time measurement of electrical parameters. This proposed system continuously monitors voltage, current, power, and energy consumption and transmits the data wirelessly using Wi-Fi. Measured parameters are visualized through the Blynk IoT platform, allowing their remote monitoring and analysis through a smartphone interface. Besides, this incorporated Telegram bot issues instant notifications, alerts, and on-demand energy usage information under different user-defined commands. This approach provides various access to user without the use of specialized hardware devices. Hence the smart energy meter is a low-cost, scalable and reliable output for residential and small commercial energy monitoring and cost utilization for the required applications. This increases energy consumption cost and energy utilization awareness, hence enabling cost reduction and proper utilization of power to meet the required cost control.